

Detecting Lifshitz Transitions Using Nonlinear Conductivity in Bilayer Graphene

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The second-order nonlinear electrical response (NLER) is an intrinsic property of inversion symmetry-broken systems which can provide deep insights into the electronic band structures of atomically thin quantum materials. However, the impact of Fermi surface reconstructions, also known as Lifshitz transitions, on the NLER has remained elusive. In this study, we investigate NLER in bilayer graphene (BLG), where the low-energy bands undergo Lifshitz transitions. Here, NLER undergoes a sign change near the Lifshitz transitions even at elevated temperatures $T \geq 10\text{K}$. At the band edge, NLER in BLG is observed to be modulated by both extrinsic scattering and interfacial-strain-induced intrinsic Berry curvature dipole, both of which can be finely tuned externally by varying doping and interlayer potential. Away from the band edge, BLG exhibits second-order conductivity exceeding $30 \mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$ at 3K, higher than any previous report. Our work establishes NLER as a reliable tool to probe Lifshitz transitions in quantum materials.

1. Introduction

The influence of the Fermi surface topology [1] on the electronic properties of conductors can be observed through classical [2], quantum Hall [3] and anomalous Hall [4] effects under time-reversal symmetry broken conditions. In inversion symmetry-broken systems, scattering mechanisms [5–10] at the Fermi surface and Berry curvature [9,11–19] of the electronic bands contribute prominently to second-order nonlinear electronic responses (or NLER) [20,21] even without time-reversal symmetry breaking. Consequently, NLER can be sensitive to topological reconstructions [12,22] in the Fermi surfaces. Unlike traditional bulk conductors, the Fermi energy (E_F) in atomically thin quantum materials can be precisely tuned across singularities in the electronic bands [23,24], known as Lifshitz transitions, where the topology of the Fermi surface changes. Recent advances suggest that NLER in two-dimensional (2D) van der Waals (vdW) crystals and their heterostructures can be exceptionally large, often surpassing that of traditional bulk crystals by orders of magnitude [6,7,25]. This enhancement opens new possibilities for NLER in logic circuits and energy-harvesting technologies [26,27]. However, there is a lack of both experimental and theoretical studies on NLER in systems where the band structure and Lifshitz transitions can be dynamically controlled by tuning thermodynamic parameters.

Bernal stacked bilayer graphene (BLG), whose low energy (E) Fermi surfaces undergo Lifshitz transitions as the E_F is varied [28–32], is an ideal system for such studies. The inversion symmetry of free-standing BLG can be broken by

hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) encapsulation and/or applying a vertical displacement field (D), which introduces a D -dependent band gap and Lifshitz transitions [30–32]. This setup fulfills the conditions necessary for scattering-mediated extrinsic NLER via side jump and skew scattering pathways [5–10,27,33]. Additionally, it leads to a finite Berry curvature [34,35], whose sign can be switched by altering the valley index (K or K'), carrier type (electron (e) or hole (h)), and the sign of D . When combined with C_3 symmetry-breaking mechanisms such as interfacial strain, BLG can also exhibit a tunable Berry curvature dipole (BCD) [36], leading to intrinsic NLER [5,9,11–18,25]. Notably, the intrinsic NLER contributes only to the transverse component, while extrinsic contributions affect both longitudinal and transverse components. Previous studies have demonstrated large extrinsic and intrinsic NLER, in graphene based systems are sensitive to Fermi surface reconstructions [6,12,22]. However, the role of Lifshitz transitions in NLER, particularly from both extrinsic and intrinsic pathways in BLG, remains unexplored.

Here we identify Lifshitz transition in BLG by observing changes in the degeneracy of the low-energy Landau level spectrum. By performing the second-order transport measurements we demonstrate that NLER changes sign near the charge neutrality point (CNP) and close to Lifshitz transitions, thereby detecting changes in Fermi surface topology. Our findings establish NLER as a powerful tool to track low-energy Lifshitz transitions in materials with broken inversion symmetry, even at elevated temperatures ($T \geq 10\text{K}$) under time-reversal symmetric conditions. Our temperature-dependent characterization reveals that near the band edges of

Figure 1. **Signature of Lifshitz transition in bilayer graphene from first order transport:** **a**, The scheme of the heterostructure is shown. **b**, $D - n$ phase space of resistivity. **c**, $\rho_{xx} - n$ data showing charge disorder density $\sim 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in gapped BLG at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.4 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$. **d**, Left panel schematically shows low energy conduction (CB) and valance (VB) of gapped BLG in the $E - k$ space in presence of an experimentally relevant finite D . i, ii, and iii indicate constant E_F planes close to the band edge. The projections of the CB at constant E_F planes are shown in the bottom, panels. This demonstrate the Lifshitz transition at $E = \epsilon_L$ (close to ii) The top middle panel show the vertical plane projection of the CB. The DoS as function of E is shown in the top right panel. **e**, The conductivity (G_{xx}) vs n at different values of vertical magnetic field (B). At larger B (7.6 T to 6.4 T) quantized G_{xx} plateaus are observed at $N \times e^2/h$ values, whereas at lower B (3.6 T to 2.4 T), 3 fold degenerate plateaus are observed at $3N \times e^2/h$ values. **f**, $B - n$ phase space (Landau Fan) of dG_{xx}/dn are shown at different values of D/ϵ_0 . $3N \times e^2/h$ plateaus are marked with white arrows. Landau level crossings (red arrows) monotonically move towards higher $|n|$ values as D/ϵ_0 increases.

BLG, NLER is governed by an interplay between intrinsic and extrinsic mechanisms. The second-order nonlinear conductivity measured in our experiments exceeds $30 \mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$, surpassing any previous reported values [6,7]. Our work provides new insights into the origin of NLER in BLG and establishes BLG as a highly tunable platform for generating NLER and exploring the physics of Lifshitz transitions.

2. Results and discussion

The dual-gated hBN/BLG/hBN field effect transistors (FETs) were fabricated using the dry transfer technique [37,38] (See Supporting Information (SI) section 1 for fabrication and sample details). **Figure 1a** depicts the schematic of the heterostructure. The measured resistivity (ρ_{xx}) at $T = 2\text{K}$ is plotted as a function of carrier density (n) and vertical displacement field (D) in Figure 1b (from sample Sa). We independently tune n and D by simultaneously controlling the top (V_{tg}) and bottom gate (V_{bg}) voltages (see experimental section and SI section 1 for details). A monotonic increase of ρ_{xx} with increasing $|D|$ indicates the band gap (E_g) opening

due to inversion symmetry breaking [39]. Figure 1c shows ρ_{xx} vs $|n|$ data, on the hole side, at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.4 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$, confirming a low charge disorder density $\sim 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (vertical dashed line). The top left panel of Figure 1d schematically shows the $E - k$ dispersion of low energy conduction (CB) and valance bands (VB) of gapped BLG at finite D [30,31]. A projection of the CB on the vertical plane is shown in the top middle panel. The corresponding density of states (DoS) is displayed in the top right panel. Horizontal pink planes (i, ii, and iii) indicate cuts of the conduction band at three different fixed Fermi energies (E_F), which are expanded in the bottom insets. The blue traces indicate the Fermi surfaces. Three low-energy Fermi pockets (in iii) merge into one (in i) via a Lifshitz transition at $E_F = \epsilon_L$, about $\sim 2 \text{ meV}$ away from the band edge (at finite D) [30,31]. The flat band at ϵ_L also leads to van Hove singularity (vHs) in the DoS. Furthermore, near ϵ_L , the slope of the $E - k$ dispersion is reversed between the inner and outer Fermi surfaces, leading to opposite velocities and effective masses for the carriers on these surfaces, thereby resulting in carrier types with opposite polarities. The objective of this work is to

Figure 2. **Second order nonlinear electrical response (NLER) in BLG:** **a** and **b**, The parabolic dependence $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ on V_{xx}^{ω} are presented at 0 and higher values of D/ϵ_0 , respectively. **c**, n dependence of $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ at $T = 10$ K with $I_{ds}^{\omega} = 100$ nA at two different values of D/ϵ_0 . The dark and light blue traces are data measured with opposite polarities of current and voltage probes, indicated schematically. **d**, simultaneously acquired n dependent $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ data are presented. **e**, Anti-symmetrized (with respect to measurement configurations) $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ vs n data is shown as blue (red) traces at two different values of D/ϵ_0 .

investigate whether NLER is sensitive to these changes resulting from the Lifshitz transitions.

We experimentally probe the Lifshitz transition in BLG by observing changes in the degeneracy of the Landau levels. Two probe conductance (G_{xx}) vs n at $D/\epsilon_0 = 0.45$ Vnm $^{-1}$ under different vertical magnetic fields (B) from is shown in Figure 1e (sample Sa). At higher values of B , G_{xx} demonstrates plateaus at $N \times e^2/h$ values (N, e , and h are integer, electronic charge, and Planck constant, respectively), corresponding to fully degeneracy-broken Landau levels. At lower values of B , we observe plateaus at $3N \times e^2/h$, corresponding to three Fermi pockets at $E_F < \epsilon_L$ [27,28]. Such changes in degeneracy, along with the emergence of a central Fermi island with opposite polarity, lead to a crossover of Landau levels [30,32] in the fan diagram of dG_{xx}/dn , far away from the disorders density as shown in Figure 1f. The plateaus corresponding $3e^2/h$ and $6e^2/h$ conductance are marked with white arrows. Landau level crossings are marked with red arrows. Our results agree well with Varlet A. et al.'s previous work [30] at similar thermodynamic conditions. These crossings are observed to shift monotonically toward higher $|n|$ values as D/ϵ_0 increases, since ϵ_L rises with D .

After detecting the Lifshitz transition using first order transport we focus on NLER, which is inevitable in an inversion symmetry-broken system [5,10]. Second-order current density is given by $j_a^{2\omega} = \sigma_{abc}^{2\omega} E_b^{\omega} E_c^{\omega}$. Here a, b, c are indices for axes. E^{ω} is the applied first-order bias. The $\sigma_{abc}^{2\omega}$, third rank tensor for second-order conductivity, is the property of the system and independent of its dimensions or applied bias. Experimentally, we apply a low-frequency (ω) ac source-drain current bias (I_{ds}^{ω}) of fixed amplitude, and

simultaneously detect transverse ($V_{xy}, V_{xy}^{2\omega}$) and longitudinal ($V_{xx}^{\omega}, V_{xx}^{2\omega}$) voltage drops at ω and 2ω frequencies using lock-in technique. We did not observe any significant ω dependence in the low ω limit (see SI section 1). The black (red) data points in Figure 2a represent V_{xx}^{ω} vs $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ data at different I_{ds}^{ω} (sample Sd), at $D = 0$ and $n = 2 \times 10^{10}$ cm $^{-2}$ (also see SI section 2). Black, red and blue points in Figure 2b shows V_{xx}^{ω} vs $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ data at higher values of D/ϵ_0 at $n = -25, -8$, and -6×10^{10} cm $^{-2}$, respectively (sample Sa). The solid lines in Figure 2a and b are parabolic fits to $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$. The n dependence of $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.1$ and -0.2 Vnm $^{-1}$ are demonstrated in Figure 2c (measured with $I_{ds}^{\omega} = 100$ nA at $T = 10$ K, from sample Sb). The dark and light blue traces having opposite signs, are acquired in measurement configurations θ (left inset) and $\theta + \pi$ (right inset), with opposite current and voltage probe polarities. The NLER has two distinctive features, (i) $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ is proportional to $V_{xx}^{\omega 2}$, and (ii) $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ changes sign if the polarities of the voltage and current probes are switched simultaneously [6–13,40]. The agreement of data shown in Figure 2a, b and c with the distinctive features (i) and (ii) unambiguously proves NLER as the origin of the observed 2ω voltage response. Simultaneously acquired $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ vs n is presented in Figure 2d (See SI section 3 for n dependence at larger D from sample Sa). Notably, $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ contains a n dependent component which does not change sign upon switching configurations from θ to $\theta + \pi$. This can originate from disorder hindering current flow in straight line, or due to thermal effects. We remove such effects by anti-symmetrizing and use $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega(a)} = (V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega})|_{\theta} -$

Figure 3. Evidence of Lifshitz transition in NLER of BLG: **a**, $n - D/\epsilon_0$ phase spaces of $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega(a)}$ at $T = 10$ K with $I_{ds}^{\omega} = 100$ nA is shown the top (bottom) left panel. The top (bottom) right panel presents the data with a reduced color scale. The black dashed lines ($n_{Lh\pm}$ and $n_{Le\pm}$) indicate sign changes in NLER capturing in the vicinity of the Lifshitz transition. n_{Lh-} in the bottom right panel indicates an additional sign change in $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$. Close to CNP ($|n| \leq 15 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), the D dependence of $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ is distinctly different from that of $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$, indicating additional intrinsic contribution in $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$. **b**, The top (bottom) panel shows $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$), along the green (brown) horizontal trace of right top (bottom) panel of **a**. The sign changes in $\sigma^{2\omega}$ are indicated with arrows **c**, Calculated $\Delta - E_F$ phase space of intrinsic 2ω conductivity σ_{yxx}^{in} for a uniaxially strained BLG. E corresponding to Lifshitz transitions ($\epsilon_{Lh\pm}^t$ and $\epsilon_{Le\pm}^t$) are marked by green dashed lines. **d**, Calculated σ_{yxx}^{in} vs E_F at $\Delta = \pm 0.05$ eV is presented, demonstrating sign changes at the Lifshitz transition.

$V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}|_{\theta+\pi}/2$ for future discussions. Figure 2e demonstrates the $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega(a)}$ vs n data as blue(red) traces. Interestingly, $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega(a)}$ changes sign at $n = 0$ detecting the transition of E_F between valence and conduction band, similar to previous reports in other graphene based systems [7,40].

To understand the evolution of NLER with band gap opening, and possible role of Lifshitz transition, we now focus on n vs D/ϵ_0 phase spaces of $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ from the same sample (Sb), which are presented in the top and bottom left panels of **Figure 3a**, respectively (at $I_{ds}^{\omega} = 100$ nA and $T = 10$ K). See **SI section 4** for $V_{xy(x)}^{\omega}$ data. Intriguingly, at positive (negative) D , the sign of $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ is observed to switch from negative (positive) to positive (negative) as n is increased from negative to positive close to CNP. Clearly in this regime ($|n| \leq 15 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), unlike $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$, the sign of $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ is dependent on the sign of D . Such distinct D dependence points towards a difference in the origin of $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$, the transverse NLER. To further elucidate the salient features in NLER, we present the data with reduced levels of the color scale in the top and bottom right panels of **Figure 3a**. In addition to the sign change close to CNP, marked as + and - lobes, $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$ also demonstrate sign changes across black dashed lines marked as $n_{Le\pm}$ and $n_{Lh\pm}$, before vanishing into experimental noise. Here, the indices $e(h)$ and $+(-)$ refer to

electron (hole) and positive (negative) D regime. In $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$, we observe an emergent sign change at n_{Lh-} . This indicates an additional emergent intrinsic NLER having $+ - -$ and $- +$ lobes at negative and positive D , respectively. The feature marked with a white arrow arises from the non-top gated BLG contacts. In the top (bottom) panel of **Figure 3b**, we show calculated second-order longitudinal (transverse) conductivity $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$) = $\frac{\sigma V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)} L}{V_{xx}^{\omega^2}} (\frac{\sigma V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)} L^2}{W V_{xx}^{\omega^2}})$ along the green (brown) horizontal sections in top (bottom) right panel of **Figure 3a**. Here L, W and σ are the length, and width of the channel and first order conductivity, respectively. The sign changes in $\sigma^{2\omega}$ are indicated with arrows. Notably, the $\sigma^{2\omega}$ is minuscule close to CNP, but increases sharply across $n_{Le\pm}$ and $n_{Lh\pm}$. The $\sigma^{2\omega}$ is related to the Fermi distribution function $f(k)$ through $\frac{\partial^2 f(k)}{\partial k_a \partial k_b}$ and $\frac{\partial f(k)}{\partial k_a}$ [5], which alters sign and magnitude close to Lifshitz transitions in BLG, particularly at the inner Fermi island with opposite carrier polarity. Our theoretically calculated skew scattering contribution to $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ (see **SI section 11**) demonstrates sign changes at only at CNP and in the vicinity of Lifshitz transitions. Furthermore, experimentally observed values of $n_{Le\pm}$ and $n_{Lh\pm}$ closely matches with previous reports in BLG at similar interlayer asymmetry [41]. Our experimental and theoretical study confirms that $n_{Le\pm}$ and $n_{Lh\pm}$ are related to Lifshitz transition. Thus, NLER in BLG can probe the low-energy Lifshitz

Figure 4. **Origin of NLER in BLG from scaling theory:** **a**, $\rho_{xx}^2 V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs ρ_{xx} data, two different D/ϵ_0 values. The solid lines are the fits using the generalized scaling equation, indicating an interplay of extrinsic side jump and skew scattering mechanisms. **b**, $\rho_{xx}^2 V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs ρ_{xx} data and fits at two different D/ϵ_0 values are shown. **c**, C_2/C_3 and C_2/C_1 from fits of $\rho_{xx}^2 V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs ρ_{xx} data at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.15$ Vnm $^{-1}$. In the scaling theory, the ratio of weightage of intrinsic NLER in the scaling parameters C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 is 1:2:1. Observed $C_2/C_3 \approx C_2/C_1 \approx 2$ indicates a dominant intrinsic contribution in $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$. **d**, C_3 vs n data at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.15$ Vnm $^{-1}$ is presented, demonstrating the sign change of intrinsic component of $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ at CNP. The solid line is a guide to the eye.

transitions even at elevated $T \geq 10$ K. In SI section 5 we compare the locations of the Landau level crossing with sign change in NLER close to the Lifshitz transition at same values of D (from samples Se and Sa). In a recent preprint [42], Chichinadze et al. also reports similar sign change in the $\sigma^{2\omega}$ in the Bernal bilayer graphene near the Lifshitz transitions, at much lower T .

The D switchable intrinsic $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ arising from BCD [12,40] can be enabled by the uncontrolled interfacial strain appearing during fabrication of vdW heterostructures [43–49]. Raman spectra from the measured samples (Sb and Sc) confirms the presence of up to 0.6% strain (see SI section 7). We theoretically calculate the intrinsic 2ω conductivity σ_{yxx}^{in} of BLG under 1% uniaxial strain (see SI section 11). Figure 3c present $E_F - \Delta$ phase space of σ_{yxx}^{in} , where $\Delta \approx ed_{vdw}D/\epsilon_0$ is the interlayer potential, e is the electronic charge and $d_{vdw} \approx 0.3$ nm. The green dashed traces denote the evolution of Lifshitz transition with increasing $|\Delta|$. σ_{yxx}^{in} demonstrates clear sign change close to the Lifshitz transitions and CNP. Additionally, σ_{yxx}^{in} also switches sign when the sign of Δ (or D) is changed, matching experimental $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$. Figure 3d represents σ_{yxx}^{in} vs E_F data at

$\Delta = \pm 0.05$ eV. Here, the grey dashed vertical lines indicate the locations of Lifshitz transitions. Our calculations qualitatively agree with experimentally observed $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ close to CNP. This indicates a significant additional intrinsic contribution to $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ close to CNP. To understand the sample-to-sample variations of our observations, we measured n vs D/ϵ_0 phase space of $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ from a different sample (sample Sc) hosting uniaxial strain (see Raman data in SI section 7). The data is presented in SI section 6, which qualitatively match with the data from sample Sb.

To further elucidate the contributions of intrinsic BCD and extrinsic mechanisms in NLER, we now focus on its ρ_{xx} dependent scaling behavior. We use T as a tuning parameter for ρ_{xx} keeping D and n values fixed. SI section 8 shows V_{xx}^{ω} and $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ vs n data at different T . At first, we focus on $V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$ which only contains extrinsic contribution. The green and the orange points in Figure 4a illustrate $\rho_{xx}^2 V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs ρ_{xx} data for $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.15$ Vnm $^{-1}$ and 0.15 Vnm $^{-1}$ at $n \approx -10 \times 10^{10}$ cm $^{-2}$, respectively. The data is well-fitted (green and orange solid lines) by the generalized disorder-induced scaling behavior of NLER (see SI section 10 for more details), $\rho_{xx}^2 \frac{V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}}{V_{xx}^{\omega^2}} = C_1 \rho_0^2 + C_2 \rho_0 \rho_T + C_3 \rho_T^2$, Here, $\rho_0 = \rho_{xx}(T \rightarrow 0)$, and $\rho_T = \rho_{xx}(T) - \rho_0$. C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are scaling parameters containing contributions of intrinsic BCD (appearing only in $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$), side jump and skew scattering from static and dynamic impurities. The intrinsic contribution has twice the weightage in C_2 , compared to that in C_1 and C_3 [5]. For orange (green) fits (in Figure 4a), values of C_1 , C_2 , C_3 are $-5.5 \times 10^{-6} \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$ ($-6.9 \times 10^{-6} \pm 3.9 \times 10^{-7}$) V $^{-1}$, and $-9.6 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.8 \times 10^{-6}$ ($-34.2 \times 10^{-6} \pm 5.1 \times 10^{-6}$) V $^{-1}$, respectively. Clearly, each parameter has the same orders of magnitude, indicating the presence of the side jump mechanism in addition to skew scattering from static and dynamic impurities. Likewise, Figure 4b presents $\rho_{xx}^2 V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs ρ_{xx} at positive (negative) D as orange (green) data points at $n = -0.03 \times 10^{12}$ cm $^{-2}$. In this case the values of C_1 , C_2 , C_3 are obtained to be $-1.5 \times 10^{-6} \pm 0.8 \times 10^{-7}$ ($1.6 \times 10^{-6} \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-8}$) V $^{-1}$, $-3.2 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.9 \times 10^{-7}$ ($3.8 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.6 \times 10^{-7}$) V $^{-1}$ and $-1.7 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.1 \times 10^{-7}$ ($2.2 \times 10^{-6} \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$) V $^{-1}$, respectively. Interestingly, here the ratio $C_1:C_2:C_3$ is observed to be $\approx 1:2:1$, for both fits. This indicates a significant contribution from the intrinsic BCD in the NLER in our BLG heterostructure close to CNP. Figure 4c presents C_2/C_3 and C_2/C_1 as a function of n . Figure 4d presents C_3 vs n demonstrating a sign change at CNP, consistent with our theoretical calculations for intrinsic contribution. Additionally, in the SI section 12, we show NLER data at higher n , measured with higher I_{ds}^{ω} to reduce experimental noise (from sample sB). We obtain $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega} > 30 \mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$ at $n = -70 \times 10^{10}$ cm $^{-2}$, at $D/\epsilon_0 = -0.125$ Vnm $^{-1}$ at $T = 3$ K which is higher than the values reported for any other 2D

vdW materials (see SI section 9) or their heterostructure to the best of our knowledge [6,7].

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, combining experiment and theoretical calculations, we demonstrated that NLER detects the sudden change in the Fermi surface topology at the Lifshitz transition near the band edge of BLG by undergoing a sign reversal. Our study reveals that NLER can be used as a general tool to locate Lifshitz transitions in inversion symmetry broken materials, even at elevated temperatures. Moreover, we show that the intrinsic Berry curvature dipole arising from interfacial strain dominates the transverse NLER close to the charge neutrality point (CNP). Furthermore, the measured second harmonic conductivity in BLG exceeds $30 \mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$, higher than that of any other 2D van der Waals materials or their heterostructures at 3K. Our work establishes BLG as a highly tunable platform for NLER and its applications.

4. Experimental section

Hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) is used as the top gate dielectric, and 300 nm SiO₂ is employed as the bottom gate dielectric (also see SI section 1). The carrier density n ($= \epsilon_0(\epsilon_{tg}(V_{tg} - V_{t0})/d_{tg} + \epsilon_{bg}(V_{bg} - V_{b0})/d_{bg})/e$) is tuned by adjusting the top (V_{tg}) and bottom (V_{bg}) gate voltages while maintaining a constant displacement field $D/\epsilon_0 = (\epsilon_{tg}(V_{tg} - V_{t0})/d_{tg} - \epsilon_{bg}(V_{bg} - V_{b0})/d_{bg})/2$. Here, e , ϵ_0 , ϵ_{tg} (d_{tg}), and ϵ_{bg} (d_{bg}) represent the electronic charge, vacuum permittivity, dielectric constant (thickness) of the top gate, and dielectric constant (thickness) of the bottom gate, respectively. V_{b0} and V_{t0} are the offset gate voltages required to reach the charge neutrality point (CNP). The top dielectric thickness d_{tg} is determined from the CNP's evolution in V_{tg} vs. V_{bg} phase space and confirmed via Hall measurements.

Electrical measurements were performed using synchronized lock-in amplifiers (also see SI section 1). We use a high series resistance ($\gg \rho_{xx}$) to convert the lock-in reference output voltage into a low-frequency current source (I_{ds}^ω). Dual-channel DC source meters were used to apply gate voltages. Experiments were conducted in a closed-cycle cryostat with a temperature range of 1.8 K – 300 K and a vertical magnetic field of ± 9 T. Transport measurements were performed in the low-frequency regime (17.77 Hz and 77.77 Hz). No significant frequency dependence was observed (also see SI section 1). We simultaneously measured the first (ω) and second 2ω harmonic voltage drops in transverse ($V_{xy}^\omega, V_{xy}^{2\omega}$) and longitudinal ($V_{xx}^\omega, V_{xx}^{2\omega}$) directions of I_{ds}^ω .

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge financial support from MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 (Grant CEX2020-001038-M), from MICIU/AEI and ERDF/EU (Projects

PID2021-122511OB-I00 and PID2021-128004NB-C21), from MICIU/AEI and European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (Grant PCI2021-122038-2A) and from the European Union (Project 101046231-FantastiCOF). T.A. acknowledges funding from the European Union under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement number 101107842 (ACCESS). H.V. acknowledges the Ministry of Education, Government of India, for funding support through the Prime Minister's Research Fellowship program. K.W. and T.T. acknowledge support from the JSPS KAKENHI (Grant Numbers 21H05233 and 23H02052) and World Premier International Research Center Initiative (WPI), MEXT, Japan.

Author contributions: T.A. and L.E.H. conceived the project. T.A. fabricated the samples, performed the measurements, and analyzed the data with assistance from B.Q.T. H.V. and A.A. performed the theory calculations. T.T. and K.W. provided the hBN crystals. T.A. and H.V. wrote the experiment and theory parts of the paper. All authors discussed, commented on the paper.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

Data availability statement

All data needed to evaluate to the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the supporting information. All source data related to the findings in this study can be obtained from the authors. All the experimental data will be uploaded to the Zenodo repository upon publication.

Keywords

Bilayer graphene, Landau level crossover, Lifshitz transitions, second-order nonlinear electrical response, Extrinsic mechanisms, Berry curvature dipole.

Supporting information

The Supporting information (SI) is available. It contains the following sections. **Section 1:** Fabrication and device details and measurement methods. **Section 2:** I_{ds}^ω dependent $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ vs n data (sample Sd) **Section 3:** $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ vs n data at larger D (sample Sa). **Section 4:** $D/\epsilon_0 - n$ phase space of $V_{xy(x)}^\omega$ (sample Sb). **Section 5:** Comparison of sign change of NLER in the vicinity of the Lifshitz transitions with the Landau level crossings. **Section 6:** $D/\epsilon_0 - n$ phase spaces of $V_{xx}^\omega, V_{xx}^{2\omega(a)}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega(a)}$ (sample Sc). **Section 7:** Evidence of strain from sample Sb and Sc. **Section 8:** $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega(a)}$ vs n data at different T from sample Sb. **Section 9:** Estimation of $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ and $\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$ (sample Sc) **Section 10:** Scaling theory of the nonlinear electrical currents. **Section 11:** Calculation of Band structure and nonlinear conductivity in strained bilayer graphene.

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